

ABSTRACT

Isolation and genomic characterization of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* phages with potential for therapeutic application

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Viruses that use bacteria as hosts are called bacteriophages or simply phages. In the lytic cycle, after replication of the phage genetic material and assembly of the particles, the viral progeny is released by complete lysis of the bacterial cell. Phages that propagate through the lytic cycle (lytic phages) have been considered a promising strategy for the biological control of infections by multidrug-resistant bacteria, including carbapenem-resistant *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (CRKP). CRKP strains have emerged as a serious public health problem worldwide in the last 10 years, and therapeutic options are limited. The main objectives of this project are: (1) to analyze the genomes of 4 clinical isolates of CRKP; (2) to use these strains to isolate lytic phages against CRKP; (3) to characterize the genomes of the isolated phages and evaluate their therapeutic potential in an animal model; and (4) to prospect for *K. pneumoniae* phage genomes in metagenomic data from the environmental sample used to isolate the phages. The 4 CRKP isolates were obtained from hospitalized patients at the Hospital das Clínicas of the USP School of Medicine. The genomes of these isolates were sequenced using MiSeq-Illumina platform prior to the start of this project and the data obtained was then used to assemble and annotate the genomes, determine the ST (Sequence Type), capsular type, resistance genes and identify plasmids. One of the isolates (K81-498) was chosen as the host strain for phage isolation. To this end, water samples were collected from the Pirajussara stream inside USP Butantan campus and used as a source for phage isolation. So far, 8 phages have been isolated from lysis plaques observed in the K81-498 culture. These phages will be purified for microbiological and genomic characterization. Both the phage DNA and the total DNA from the water samples will be extracted and sequenced on the Illumina platform. Our expectation is that within a few months we will have the sequencing data available to follow up on the project's objectives, which will enable the genomic characterization of the isolated phages for potential clinical use in the treatment of CRKP infections. At the same time, we will also be recovering phage genomes from the environmental sample used to isolate the phages from *K. pneumoniae*.

Keywords: *Klebsiella pneumoniae*; Antibiotic Resistance; Bacteriophage; Metagenomics.

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